

Navayana Buddhism

also known as “Ambedkarite Buddhism”, “Dalit Buddhism”, “Neo-/New-/New Vehicle Buddhism”

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Entry tags: Modern Buddhism, Religious Group, Ambedkarite Buddhism, Dalit Religion, Language, English, Buddhist Traditions, South Asian Religion, Convert Religion, Anti-caste Religion, Modern Marathi, Eastern Hindi, Tamil-Kannada

Navayana Buddhism is an interpretation of Buddhism popularized by Dr. Bhimrao Ramji Ambedkar (1891-1956)--India's constitutionalist, political visionary, economist, and anti-caste activist--for the upliftment of the low-caste Dalit community. While the history of Buddhism is much older, the history of Navayana Buddhism effectively began in 1956 with the mass conversion of millions of Dalits under the leadership of Dr. Ambedkar. The mass conversion occurred in Nagpur, a city in the present-day state of Maharashtra, India. Today, Navayana Buddhism is a global community. The bibliography includes readings on Navayana Buddhism in Myanmar, Thailand, London, Sri Lanka, the U.S.A., and several states of India, especially Maharashtra and Uttar Pradesh where most Navayana Buddhists reside. Reverence for the Buddha, Dr. Ambedkar's anti-caste work, and caste consciousness are foundational to Navayana Buddhist beliefs and practices.

Date Range: 1956 CE - 2024 CE

Region: Global, India, Maharashtra

Region tags: Maharashtra, Global, India

The mass conversion of Dalits into Navayana Buddhism took place in Nagpur, a city in the present-day state of Maharashtra, India. Today, Navayana Buddhism is a global community. The bibliography includes readings on Navayana Buddhism in Myanmar, Thailand, London, Sri Lanka, the U.S.A., and several states of India, especially Maharashtra and Uttar Pradesh where a majority of Navayana Buddhists reside.

Status of Participants:

✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Omvedt, Gail. *Buddhism in India: Challenging Brahmanism and Caste*. New Delhi: Sage Publications, 2003.
- Source 2: Zelliott, Eleanor. *Ambedkar's Conversion*. New Delhi: Critical Quest, 2007.
- Source 3: Bodhi, S. R. *Dialogues on Basics in Buddhism: A Navayana (New Vehicle) Approach*. Nagpur: New Vehicle Publications, 2023.

Notes: See the bibliography for more print sources on Navayana Buddhism.

Online sources for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: <https://baws.in/>

– Source 1 Description: This is an online database of Dr. Ambedkar's writings and speeches hosted by the Ambedkar International Center, U.S.A. It also includes relevant secondary sources.

– Source 2 URL: <https://franpritchett.com/00ambedkar/timeline/index.html>

– Source 2 Description: This is a timeline of Dr. Ambedkar's life and works. It draws on primary and secondary sources. It also contains links to scholarly essays, translations of Marathi biographies, and films on Dr. Ambedkar and Navayana Buddhism.

– Source 3 URL: <https://exhibitions.library.columbia.edu/exhibits/show/ambedkar/dalits>

– Source 3 Description: This is a list of websites that address issues related to the international community of Dalits (not limited to Navayana Buddhists).

Notes: Equality Labs is a South Asian Dalit civil rights organization: <https://www.equalitylabs.org/>

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

– Source 1 URL: <https://baws.in/>

– Source 1 Description: This is an online database of Dr. Ambedkar's writings and speeches hosted by the Ambedkar International Center, U.S.A. It includes relevant secondary sources.

– Source 2 URL: <https://www.mea.gov.in/books-writings-of-ambedkar.htm>

– Source 2 Description: This website has 17 volumes of Dr. Ambedkar's writings and speeches in English, and 40 volumes in Hindi, as well as audio books.

– Source 3 URL: <http://www.ambedkar.org/>

– Source 3 Description: This is one of the largest Dalit-Bahujan media databases.

Notes: A recent critical edition of *The Buddha and His Dhamma* by Aakash Singh Rathore and Ajay Verma can be found here: <https://global.oup.com/academic/product/the-buddha-and-his-dhamma-9780198068679?cc=ca&lang=en&>

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Is the cultural contact competitive:

– Yes

Notes: While Navayana Buddhists have already opted out of Hinduism in favor of Buddhism, it is important to note that Dalit communities are vulnerable to a broad and highly competitive market of religious conversion that targets low-caste communities.

↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– No

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

– No

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– Yes

Notes: The following news article covers a recent incident of violent conflict between a large residential area of Navayana Buddhists and others, and law enforcement in the midst of electoral politics: <https://en.themooknayak.com/dalit-news/jai-bhim-nagar-slum-demolition-rajratna-ambekar-stages-sit-in-protest-claims-homes-of-non-bjp-voters-targeted>

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– Yes

Notes: Dalits and Navayana Buddhists have been vulnerable to assaults from external groups. An example of a recent incident is the 2018 Bhima Koregaon violence. Professor Shraddha Kumbhojkar at the Savitribai Phule Pune University has written about the history of the Bhima Koregaon memorial: <https://www.epw.in/journal/2012/42/special-articles/contesting-power-contesting-memories.html>

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– I don't know

Notes: More research needs to be done on the processes/systems involved in assigning religious affiliation. As far as my research goes, Navayana Buddhists are born or married into Navayana Buddhist families. Religious affiliation is assigned and performed through Ambedkarite Buddhist iconography and Ambedkar worship.

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: More research needs to be done on what constitutes active proselytization in the context of Navayana Buddhism. I am aware of marriage being a method of recruiting new members to Navayana Buddhism, and there have been several instances of mass conversion to Navayana Buddhism led by anti-caste activists.

Does the religion have official political support

– I don't know

Notes: This question cannot be answered without a clearly defined context. Broadly, Hindutva ideology and its adhering political parties such as the BJP do not explicitly support Navayana Buddhists. More specifically, for instance, the Ambedkarite politician, Chandrashekhar Azad, did win the 2024 Lok Sabha elections in Uttar Pradesh, where the BJP had been attempting to garner popular support. While Azad's political party positions itself as an Ambedkarite one, it does not officially and exclusively

support Navayana Buddhism. It supports Dalit communities.

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– I don't know

Notes: This question is difficult to answer. Dr. Ambedkar eschewed Hinduism in favor of Navayana Buddhism. I am not sure if Navayana Buddhists today adhere to a conception of apostasy.

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Estimated population, numeric: 7000000

Notes: This is the approximate number of Buddhists in Maharashtra according to the 2011 population census. Please see the bibliography to access the census data. A large population of Navayana Buddhists resides in Maharashtra following Dr. Ambedkar's conversion, and smaller numbers reside in other states, especially Karnataka, Uttar Pradesh, Madhya Pradesh, Gujarat, and Tamil Nadu. According to the 2011 census, the total population of Buddhists in India is around 8.4 million, which is 0.7% of the total population of India. 5.81% of the total population of Maharashtra is Buddhist, 0.16% in Karnataka, 0.05% in Gujarat, and 0.02% in Tamil Nadu. Navayana Buddhism is a growing international community with significant numbers residing in Myanmar, Sri Lanka, the UK, the USA, and Canada. There is no data on the Navayana Buddhist diaspora. The 2021 census was delayed owing to the pandemic. The results of an ongoing effort to conduct a census will be released by the end of 2024. These results will be insightful because there have been several mass conversions into Dalit Buddhism in the recent past. See: 1)<https://indianexpress.com/article/cities/ahmedabad/thousands-embrace-buddhism-in-event-organised-by-dalit-body-8556880/> 2)<https://utsnyc.edu/when-a-million-buddhist-dalits-come-to-town-part-2/> 3)<https://www.ucanews.com/news/india-makes-it-difficult-for-dalits-to-convert-to-buddhism/104758> 4)<https://en.themooknayak.com/dalit-news/in-the-suburbs-of-bengaluru-3000-dalits-are-set-to-denounce-hinduism-and-embrace-the-buddhist-way-of-life> 5)<https://wwwn.org/articles/13659/>

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Estimated population, percentage of sample region: 0.07

Notes: According to the 2011 census, the total population of Buddhists in India is around 8.4 million, which is 0.7% of the total population. It is important to remember that not all Buddhists in India are Navayana Buddhists. We do not have clear census data of the % population of Navayana Buddhism. The northeastern states of India have the largest concentration of non-Navayana Buddhists. Maharashtra has the largest concentration of Navayana Buddhists following Dr. Ambedkar's conversion. See the previous answer and the census report in the bibliography for more details.

Nature of religious group [please select one]:

– Small religious group (actively discouraged-suppressed by larger religious group(s))

Notes: According to the 2011 census, Buddhists are a minority community in all states of India except for Sikkim and Arunachal Pradesh. Navayana Buddhists are a minor fraction of the total Buddhist population in India. Conversion out of Hinduism is actively discouraged and suppressed in India today.

Nathaniel Roberts has discussed public debates and legislation related to religious conversion out of Hinduism (and into Buddhism and Christianity) in the context of Dr. Ambedkar's movement. Please see his and Lucinda Ramberg's (forthcoming) work on the southern regions of India, along with Eleanor Zelliot, Gail Omvedt, and Anupama Rao's work on Maharashtra. Also see: <https://www.ucanews.com/news/india-makes-it-difficult-for-dalits-to-convert-to-buddhism/104758>

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Dr. Ambedkar is recognized as the leader of Navayana Buddhism, and the Buddha is recognized as the leader of Buddhism writ large. Mass conversions are led by local anti-caste leaders today. The nature of reverence to the Dr. Ambedkar differs per region and language. In some cases, Dr. Ambedkar is considered to be a god. In some other cases, especially in the tight-knit community of his own comrades in the late nineteenth and early twentieth century, Dr. Ambedkar was considered a political leader, and in that sense fallible, vulnerable, and human. To get a detailed sense of Dr. Ambedkar as a political leader before he converted to Buddhism, his processes of and arguments for conversion, and the aftermath of his conversion in 1956 in Nagpur along with approximately 500000 followers, see the following digital database: <https://franpritchett.com/00ambedkar/timeline/index.html>

↳ Is there a hierarchy among these leaders:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There may be hierarchies in specific contexts of Navayana Buddhist practice.

↳ Are leaders believed to possess supernatural powers or qualities:

– No

↳ Are religious leaders chosen:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Religious leaders are generally chosen via popular support and the leader's own organizational efforts. Dr. Ambedkar emphasized leadership, organization, and agitation.

↳ Are leaders considered fallible:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Leaders are fallible in the sense that they are human and likely to gain or lose popular support. More research needs to be done on this topic.

↳ Are close followers or disciples of a religious leader required to obediently and unquestionably accept the leader's pronouncements on all matters:

– No

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also “oral scriptures” (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

Notes: The answer to this question is a qualified yes. Dr. Ambedkar wrote *The Buddha and His Dhamma*, which was published posthumously in 1957. It can be accessed here: https://franpritchett.com/00ambedkar/ambedkar_buddha/index.html This text is considered scripture by Navayana Buddhists. It is a modern scripture in the sense that it explains, through deep engagement with scholarly literature and debates, how Navayana Buddhism is distinct from early Buddhism. It is an interpretative scripture meant specifically to address questions of Dalit freedom and equality, and is part of Dr. Ambedkar's larger effort to organize Dalits. Dr. Ambedkar wrote several other treatises that can be considered scripture in the same way, but have not received the level of popularity that *The Buddha and His Dhamma* has. Dr. Ambedkar's writings, speeches, and other forms of popular media like pamphlets can be explored here: <https://baws.in/> The 22 oaths that Dr. Ambedkar took are considered foundational to the beliefs and practices of Navayana Buddhism: 1. I shall have no faith in Brahma, Vishnu and Mahesh, nor shall I worship them. 2. I shall have no faith in Rama and Krishna, nor shall I worship them. 3. I shall have no faith in 'Gouri', 'Ganpathi' and other Gods and Goddesses of Hindu religion, nor shall I worship them. 4. I do not believe in the theory of incarnation of Gods. 5. I do not and shall not believe that the Lord Buddha was the incarnation of Vishnu. I believe this to be, mischievous and false propaganda. 6. I shall not perform 'Shraaddha' nor, shall I give 'pind- dan'.* 7. I shall not act in any manner contrary to the principles and teachings of the Buddha. 8. I shall not perform any ceremony through Brahmins. 9. I believe in the equality of mankind. 10. I shall endeavour to establish equality. 11. I shall follow the Eightfold Path taught by the Buddha. 12. I shall follow the 'Ten Paramitas' enunciated by the Buddha. 13. I shall be compassionate to all living beings and nurture them with care. 14. I shall not steal. 15. I shall not lie. 16. I shall not commit carnal sins. 17. I shall not consume liquor. 18. I shall strive to lead my life in conformity with the three principles of Buddhism i. e. Pradnya (wisdom), Sheel (character) and Karuna (compassion). 19. I hereby embrace Buddhism by renouncing my old Hindu religion which is detrimental to the prosperity to the humankind and descriminate human beings and treat them low. 20. I firmly believe that the Buddha Dhamma is the Saddhamma. 21. I believe, I am entering the new life. 22. Hereafter I pledge to conduct myself in accordance with the teachings of the Buddha.

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

↳ Are they oral:

– No

↳ Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:

– Yes

↳ Revealed by a high god:

– No

↳ Revealed by other supernatural being:

– No

↳ Inspired by high god:

– No

↳ Inspired by other supernatural being:

– No

↳ Originated from divine or semi-divine human beings:

– No

Notes: See the next answer.

↳ Originated from non-divine human being:

– Yes

Notes: Navayana Buddhism is a decidedly human interpretation--informed by Dr. Ambedkar's critique of class and caste relations and concerns for the Dalit community's future in post-colonial India--of Buddhism. The Buddha and Dr. Ambedkar are understood to be non-divine human beings in the sense that their biographical narratives, political visions, and daily practices are deeply intertwined with historical human relations. That is, the Buddha and Dr. Ambedkar are not supernatural. However, they are worshipped as special, god-like humans.

↳ Are the scriptures alterable:

– No

↳ Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders) for interpreting the scriptures:

– No

↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures:

– No

↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures:

– No

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Most Buddhist architecture dates Dr. Ambedkar's invention of Navayana Buddhism. However, there are several religious sites that Navayana Buddhists visit on important days. These sites include locations where Dr. Ambedkar protested caste discrimination (like Mahad, where Dr. Ambedkar fought for untouchables' access to water), sites of historical significance for low-caste military participation (like Bhima Koregaon), as well as statues of Dr. Ambedkar that have become integral parts of public spaces in India. The topic of Navayana Buddhist architecture, as distinct from historical Buddhist architecture, is yet to be studied in much depth.

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– No

Notes: See the previous answer.

Is iconography present:

– Yes

↳ Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:

– On persons

– At home

– Some public spaces

Notes: Images of Dr. Ambedkar are the most commonly seen Navayana Buddhist iconography. His photos, statues, calendar art, pamphlets, paintings, etc. are all worshipped, along with the Buddha's.

↳ Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography:

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not):

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic):

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic):

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic):

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract symbol):

– No

↳ Portrayals of afterlife:

– No

Notes: Navayana Buddhism rejects rebirth and reincarnation.

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols):

– No

↳ Humans:

– Yes

Notes: A distinct feature of Navayana Buddhism is that when Dr. Ambedkar is worshipped, he is most frequently presented as a human figure through images, art, statues, and iconography. Barring images of Dr. Ambedkar dressed as a Buddhist monk, the most widely circulated iconography of Navayana Buddhism includes Dr. Ambedkar in a blue suit with his iconic spectacles and an austere stance. See, <https://www.symbiosis-ambedkarmemorial.org/about.php>

↳ Other features of iconography:

– Yes

Notes: A specific blue color is especially associated with Navayana Buddhism. See the following artist's work for examples of this blue: <https://artreview.com/vikrant-bhise-the-dalit-struggle-is-a-universal-struggle/> Also see the images on @DalitHistory: https://www.instagram.com/dalit_history/p/CTZcHg3Pe-m/?img_index=1

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Most Buddhist architecture dates Dr. Ambedkar's invention of Navayana Buddhism. However, there are several religious sites that Navayana Buddhists visit on important days. These sites include locations where Dr. Ambedkar protested caste discrimination (like Mahad, where Dr. Ambedkar fought for untouchables' access to water), sites of historical significance for low-caste military participation (like Bhima Koregaon), as well as statues of Dr. Ambedkar that have become integral parts of public spaces in India. The topic of Navayana Buddhist architecture and contemporary sites of worship as distinct from historical Buddhism is yet to be studied in much depth.

Are pilgrimages present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: More research needs to be done on this issue. On important days, like Dr. Ambedkar's birth and death anniversaries, there are several rallies that may look like pilgrimages but are distinct in ethos, practice, participation, and caste politics from other contemporary pilgrimages (such as those that take place during the Ganapati festival in Maharashtra, for instance).

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer “no” only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Notes: Dr. Ambedkar distinguishes between the body and the energy that animates it. He says that the Buddha believed in a no-soul theory. See *The Buddha and His Dhamma*, Book IV, Part II, Sections I, II, and III. Dr. Ambedkar argued that the Buddha's no-soul theory is scientifically sound.

Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Yes

Notes: The body comprises four elements (earth, water, air, and fire). See *The Buddha and His Dhamma*, Book IV, Part II, Section I. Energy (not soul or spirit) animates these four elements.

Belief in afterlife:

– No

Notes: Dr. Ambedkar highlights the Buddha's no-soul theory for Navayana Buddhism. He argues that the body may be reborn, but never as the same person. See *The Buddha and His Dhamma*, Book IV, Part II, Sections, I, II, and III.

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– I don't know

Notes: This question cannot be answered without context. In *The Buddha and His Dhamma*, the Buddha's corpse is burnt and the ashes are collected. See Book VII, Part III. I do not know how Navayana Buddhists today treat their corpses.

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– I don't know

Notes: See the previous answer.

Are grave goods present:

– I don't know

Notes: See the previous answer.

Are formal burials present:

– I don't know

Notes: See the previous answer.

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– No

Notes: As I have mentioned earlier, Navayana Buddhism is Dr. Ambedkar's specific interpretation of Buddhism that focuses on caste and class relations of humans. Supernatural beings are not important in this framework.

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– No

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– No

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– No

Is an eschatology present:

– No

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: The Buddha and His Dhamma outlines 'Saddhamma,' the good way to live for a Navayana Buddhist. These norms oppose and are antidotes to those of the caste and class system that Dr. Ambedkar sought to critique.

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– Yes

↳ What is the nature of this distinction:

– Strongly present and highlighted

Notes: The conventional norms of the caste and class system are distinguished from those of the Saddhamma that Dr. Ambedkar highlights through the Buddha's life story.

↳ Are specifically moral norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: The Buddha and His Dhamma outlines these norms.

↳ Specifically moral norms are implicitly linked to vague metaphysical concepts:

– No

↳ Specifically moral norms are explicitly linked to vague metaphysical entities:

– No

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked to impersonal cosmic order (e.g. karma):

– Yes

Notes: Dr. Ambedkar proposes a critique of the Hindu cosmic order wherein one's karmas determine (and are used to justify) one's place in the caste system. Dr. Ambedkar specifically de-links Navayana Buddhism from this cosmic order.

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked in some way to an anthropomorphic being:

– Yes

Notes: The moral norms are linked to the life of the Buddha.

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked explicitly to commands of anthropomorphic being:

– No

Notes: Dr. Ambedkar's commands and his interpretation of the Buddha's commands together make the core of Navayana Buddhism.

- ↳ Specifically moral norms are have no special connection to metaphysical:
 - No

- ↳ Moral norms apply to:
 - All individuals within contemporary world

Notes: The Buddha and His Dhamma is written as a universal religion while specifically addressing the Dalit community in the context of the newly formed Indian nation-state. It is proposed that all individuals within the contemporary world can eschew their religions and accept the Navayana Buddhist way of life.

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Equality of all castes and classes.

- ↳ Honesty / trustworthiness / integrity:
 - No

- ↳ Courage (in battle):
 - No

- ↳ Courage (generic):
 - No

- ↳ Compassion / empathy / kindness / benevolence:
 - Yes

- ↳ Mercy / forgiveness / tolerance:
 - No

- ↳ Generosity / charity:
 - No

- ↳ Selflessness / selfless giving:
 - No

- ↳ Righteousness / moral rectitude:
 - No

↳ Ritual purity / ritual adherence / abstention from sources of impurity:

– No

↳ Respectfulness / courtesy:

– No

↳ Familial obedience / filial piety:

– No

↳ Fidelity / loyalty:

– No

↳ Cooperation:

– No

↳ Independence / creativity / freedom:

– Yes

↳ Moderation / frugality:

– No

↳ Forbearance / fortitude / patience:

– No

↳ Diligence / self-discipline / excellence:

– No

↳ Assertiveness / decisiveness / confidence / initiative:

– Yes

↳ Strength (physical):

– No

↳ Power / status / nobility:

– No

- ↳ Humility / modesty:
 - No
- ↳ Contentment / serenity / equanimity:
 - No
- ↳ Joyfulness / enthusiasm / cheerfulness:
 - No
- ↳ Optimism / hope:
 - No
- ↳ Gratitude / thankfulness:
 - No
- ↳ Reverence / awe / wonder:
 - No
- ↳ Faith / belief / trust / devotion:
 - No
- ↳ Wisdom / understanding:
 - Yes
- ↳ Discernment / intelligence:
 - Yes
- ↳ Beauty / attractiveness:
 - No
- ↳ Cleanliness (physical) / orderliness:
 - No
- ↳ Other important virtues advocated by the religious group:
 - Yes [specify]: Dr. Ambedkar emphasized the values of education, organization, and agitation.

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Yes

Notes: The Buddha and His Dhamma outlines the ethical precepts of Saddharma--the good way of living--in Book III. If I am to briefly and crudely summarize what these ethical precepts are, they are class equality, caste equality, and kindness.

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Notes: In principle, Navayana Buddhism is open to all castes and classes via conversion.

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– No

Notes: While the religious group does not require participation in any rituals, its members do indeed participate in household rituals like pujas. Dr. Ambedkar and his wife Ramabai, prior to Dr. Ambedkar's conversion, did several household rituals. Ramabai is said to have started the practice of worshipping Dr. Ambedkar's framed photo, a practice that many contemporary Navayana Buddhists follow.

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

I.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale "ceremonies" and "festivals."

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– No

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– No

Notes: While the group does not employ fictive kinship terminology, the Sangha (the community or fraternity) is an important concept in Book V of The Buddha and His Dhamma.

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– Other [specify in comments]

Notes: I would argue that the society to which Navayana Buddhists belong is best characterized as a caste. When Dr. Ambedkar converted to Navayana Buddhism, he did so with the specific objective of uplifting and organizing the caste-group he referred to as Dalits (the downtrodden). Dalits (characterized as avarna or without-varna) have traditionally been relegated to the fringes of caste society (characterized as savarna or with-varna). By the time Dr. Ambedkar proposed a critique of the savarna order by converting to Navayana Buddhism, thereby reforming Hinduism as well as Buddhism, processes of consolidating South Asian societies through caste-concepts, regulative state mechanisms, and popular movements into caste-based social realities were already underway.

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– No

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– I don't know

Notes: Famine relief should, in principle, be made available to the group's adherents by the state. I do not know more about this topic.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– No

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– No

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– No

Notes: See section on 'Written Language.'

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: See section on 'Written Language.'

Is extra-religious education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Notes: See section on 'Written Language.'

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Notes: In so far as Navayana Buddhists are citizens of a nation-state, they interact with national and state bureaucracies.

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– No

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– No

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: In so far as Navayana Buddhists are citizens of a nation-state, taxes are levied on them by the respective nation-state.

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: In so far as Navayana Buddhists reside in the Indian nation-state, or any nation-state for that matter (such as Tamil Dalits in Srilanka), they interact with and are especially vulnerable to persecution at the hands of national police forces owing to systemic forms of caste oppression and bias. Gail Omvedt has written about how Dalit Buddhists were affected by the 'Namantar Andolan' and subsequent riots and police brutality in the 1970s, 80s, and 90s. See *Reinventing Revolution* in the bibliography and Anand Patwardhan's documentary film *Jai Bhim Comrade*.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: In so far as Navayana Buddhists reside in the Indian nation-state, or any nation-state for that matter, they interact with state judicial systems.

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: In so far as Navayana Buddhists reside in the Indian nation-state, or any nation-state for that matter, they are subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by the nation-state and its many functionaries.

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Notes: Navayana Buddhists do not have a formal legal code. They are, as I have mentioned earlier, in principle, committed to the 22 oaths that Dr. Ambedkar outlined when he converted to Navayana Buddhism. The 22 oaths (publicly announced in the 1950s) are undergirded by a critique of the Hindu code of law around which Dr. Ambedkar began mobilizing the Dalit community in the 1920s. The

Hindu code of law is articulated in a large body of literature called the Dharmasastras. Dr. Ambedkar publicly burnt a copy of the Manusmriti, a treatise that articulates the norms of what we refer to as the caste system today. With this said, Dr. Ambedkar conceptualized Navayana Buddhism in explicit rejection of the Hindu legal code as seen in the Manusmriti. See Sharmila Rege's *Against the Madness of Manu* for more on Ambedkar's eschewal of the Hindu code of law.

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: This is an important question to understand the pre-history of modern Dalit communities of which Navayana Buddhism is one specific iteration. In colonial South Asia, Dalit men were employed by the British Marine Battalion since the early 19th century. Low-caste men were also employed by pre-colonial armies such as those of the Peshwas and the Marathas. Military employment provided pathways of upward mobility that were not available to Dalits in other public and largely upper-caste spaces. Dr. Ambedkar's father retired from the British army in 1894. Dr. Ambedkar was born in the British-founded town of Mhow, an important military center near Indore, Madhya Pradesh. His early schooling was done in several different public schools in Maharashtra's military centers. While Dr. Ambedkar was not himself in the army, and there is little research on Navayana Buddhists enrolled in the Indian army today, we know that armies since pre-British colonial times up to the present have been important avenues for Dalit community formation and the public articulation of caste critiques and negotiations. The 1857 mutiny is a case in point. See the following for more on institutionalized militaries and anti-colonial and anti-caste mobilization in South Asia:
<https://westportlibrary.libguides.com/IndianRebellionof1857>

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an

institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Traditional systems of learning and Hindu religious exposition (with exceptions) discriminated against low-caste learners. The history of casteism is, fundamentally, a history of how certain castes were forced into illiteracy. Baby Kamble's autobiography *The Prisons We Broke* gives us insight into how illiteracy is sustained in the Dalit community. When Dr. Ambedkar proposed mass conversion to Buddhism, he emphasized schooling and higher education in English for the Dalit community. His personal pursuits, since the 1910s, involved doing a Ph.D. from Columbia University (New York) and the London School of Economics. His persona as an English-speaking and highly qualified intellectual was central to his political activism and leadership. Navayana Buddhists, today, have access to education in English and other regional vernaculars (in government and private institutions, as well as domestic and other informal spaces). However, systemic exclusion and oppression continue to persist.

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: See the previous answer. Pathways for Navayana Buddhists to become adept in all the major non-religion-specific languages are available. However, it is important to emphasize that processes of educating those who have been peripheral to the caste system through modern educational institutions have been marred by systemic forms of casteist exclusion. See Shailaja Paik's work in the bibliography for more on this topic.

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– No

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

– Other [specify in comments]

Notes: Inter-caste commensality has been highly regulated by the caste system. The lowest rungs of the caste system, many of whom are now Navayana Buddhist, have been at the receiving end of caste discrimination in the form of forced starvation, lack of access to specific kinds of foods, spatial segregation, and untouchability (specifically, banning Dalits from touching or being around specific foods, production spaces, and practices). Dalits, therefore,

have had a separate, rich, and unique tradition of cooking. Here are a few resources on dalit cooking: 1) <https://www.rajyashrigoody.com/is-hunger-gnawing-at-your-belly> 2) <https://homegrown.co.in/homegrown-explore/dalit-identity-and-food-memories-of-trauma-on-a-plate> 3) <https://www.goya.in/blog/blood-fry-other-recipes-from-my-dalit-childhood>

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– I don't know

Notes: I do not know any instances of non-Dalit institutions providing Navayana Buddhists or Dalits food.

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